
Sustainable Entrepreneurship in E-Commerce and Their Impact on Environmental Sustainability

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Abstract:

Businesses have been expected to pave the way towards environmental sustainability due to their notably significant contribution towards polluting the environment through waste, gas emissions and plastics generated. The responsibility does not necessarily begin with one individual within a business though— employees at every level of the business must work together to bring about change. Green Business entrepreneur achieving popularity day by day. It is the new buzzword in business. Though the concept of green business is not new, but it is becoming increasingly vital in today's business climate. The world is going green and so are the companies. Now going green has become the new success mantra in market to differentiate the products and services from their competition. It has also become a platform for innovation.

Keywords: *Sustainable Entrepreneurship, Effects on Environment, Eco – friendly Business.*

Introduction:

Sustainable entrepreneurship in e-commerce is the practice of developing and selling products in an environmentally and socially responsible way. It involves creating a profitable business while also helping society and the planet. Sustainable development is based on the three pillars of sustainability: **economic**, **environmental** and **social** sustainability. Environmental sustainability encourages people to live in a way that doesn't put stress on natural resources. But does that mean the term 'sustainable e-commerce' is contradictory, given shopping encourages the consumption of materials.

That all depends on the individual business's practices. Any brand that's truly dedicated to sustainable e-commerce will outline transparent plans on how it aims to lower emissions, avoid unnecessary packaging, and generally reduce its impact on the planet.

adopting sustainable e-commerce as part of the business strategy here are the best ways we can do it:

- Reduce unnecessary packaging
- Offset your impact
- Lower your transport emissions
- Empower your customers
- Remove recycling barriers
- Reducing returns
- Try “e-commerce”
- Host your e-commerce site on a green platform

E-commerce businesses generally produce fewer emissions than in-person stores (also known as brick-and-mortar

stores). The study carried out by MIT found ecommerce to be more sustainable than traditional retail in more than 75% of the scenarios developed in their base case. Another study suggests that online shopping at large retailers in the US is 17% more carbon-efficient than visiting traditional stores.

Literature Review:

A. Concept and Implementation of E-commerce E-commerce has been regarded as the activity of buying and selling products and services using the internet. The business model is designed in a way that it provides its offerings online and gives the opportunity to the consumers for selecting and purchasing the desired products. Planning for Ecommerce business is critical as this allows the firm to take into consideration the related dynamics and implementation of the business model, consider the probable adversities and challenges that may arise during the process and functionality. The planning further considers the associated risks and limitations which the company may be exposed to and so an effective contingency plan may be developed through critical planning and considerations. The other aspect is technology selection along with mediums and approaches. To function online, it is vital that the firm selects the most adequate technology to carry out the desired tasks and activities. In this regard, the considerations need to be made in accordance with the nature and type of customers along with the capabilities, resources, and kind of business that is involved in the process. The technology usage may differ for varied businesses and their specific target audiences and a critical analysis in this regard could be conducted to ensure optimum results. E-commerce Business Model Source Customer acquisition could be regarded as another critical element related to the implementation of Ecommerce. Businesses

use a huge range of tools for reaching out to consumers such as search engine marketing, display advertisement, email campaigns, social media marketing, and much more. With regards to the sales principle of awareness, interest, desire, and action (AIDA) it could be noted that customer acquisition cost will be higher for the brands that are new in the market, and in comparison, it would be lower for those that have already established an offline presence in the industry. Customer engagement is another imperative dynamic related to the successful implementation of Ecommerce. The fact that customer concerns and requirements are constantly evolving, it has become vital for businesses to make sure that their developed online business model has the ability and features of providing a robust support mechanism for queries, issues, and information to the consumers. In this regard, social media presence has been identified to be a successful approach to catering to such concerns and effectively implementing online business activities.

Benefits Of Using Sustainable E-Commerce For Business:

Sustainable ecommerce doesn't just benefit the environment and conscious consumers — the company itself can benefit too.

Here are the top benefits of having sustainable ecommerce in a business strategy:

Attracts more customers – More shoppers are choosing sustainability as a metric for whether or not they want to support a brand. In fact, there was a 71% increase in Google searches for sustainable goods between 2016 and 2021

Reduces impact on the planet – By cutting back on plastic packaging businesses can reduce the amount of fossil fuels they rely on, and the amount of natural resources they consume

Saves money – Running factories and warehouses on renewable energy can be cheaper for businesses, especially if they switch to either solar or wind power. Similarly, using electric vehicles to deliver ecommerce goods can cut fuel costs

Attracts more employees – 71% of employees and employment seekers say that environmentally sustainable companies are more attractive prospects, according to a survey by the IBM Institute for Business Value (IBV). And nearly half of people surveyed said they would accept a lower salary to work for these organizations

Prepares businesses for the future – Fossil fuels are finite, which means businesses will have to make the switch to more sustainable practices in the near future. These changes have already started to happen too, with governments around the world announcing tighter laws on unsustainable business practices

Can reduce tax – Some countries, such as the UK, offer tax incentives for any businesses that are switching to more sustainable processes

Usage and Significance of E-Commerce Business on Environment:

E-commerce has resulted in being a highly imperative concept for businesses in the modern world. Organisations can make use of the technology to not only reach out to a higher set of audiences but also increase the effectiveness and efficiency of work.

The elimination of geographical boundaries has been the core use and significance of Ecommerce that has allowed organisations to expand their work operations and effectively carry out market development.

Firms have been making use of global consumer base and identify the demand of their products and services in various markets of the world. In the emerging economy, E-commerce has resulted in being a necessary and vital element of business strategy.

E-commerce has caused downward pressure on inflation due to increased competition and cost savings. With more and more businesses establishing their presence in the industry through Ecommerce, the prices of products and services have reduced.

Competition has influenced companies to keep their prices at a minimum because customers have ample substitutes in the market.

E-commerce has made it easier for companies to set-up their presence and start their businesses due to lesser investment requirements and easier operations. With E-commerce, organisations have been able to start their projects and start functioning at a small scale.

Due to no need of developing a physical presence, lesser initial capital and investment is required and this promotes business start-ups.

With a higher number of E-commerce businesses taking place, more jobs are created in the economy and better employment rates are established.

Customers on the other hand are given a good purchase experience through which they can easily go through a huge variety of products and chose their required goods and services without any hassle or wastage of time.

E-commerce has changed the way businesses used to carry out their operational and functional activities, allowing organisations to optimize on various opportunities. Going global, a huge number of businesses have been able to enter new markets and make use of higher outreach overall.

Further, internet technology for businesses allows them to improve their communication and allow doing business more easily. Earlier, it was highly challenging for customers to interact or communicate with companies or present their concerns.

Reaching out to businesses and forwarding the concerns to the right authorities was considered daunting for consumers and this often led to dissatisfaction between individuals. Also, the whole process of communication was very time taking and lengthy which restricted consumers from presenting their queries to the firms or give their feedback for improvements.

E-commerce has made it much easier and feasible for consumers to interact with the companies and put forward their concerns regarding the products and services. Using the internet, customers can easily communicate with the concerned authorities and attain prompt responses from the brand.

This has allowed businesses to achieve high customer satisfaction and retain consumers for a longer period. Considering that customer retention is difficult in the contemporary environment, effective communication results in adding value to this aspect.

Conclusion:

E-commerce has changed the way businesses used to operate and function. Organisations have been able to attain various opportunities and benefits on which they have optimized to attain a good position

and image in the marketplace. With regards to business performance, it has been identified that firms are able to significantly augment their performance level due to increased marketplace, better growth opportunities, lesser operating costs, a fewer requirement of investments, lesser risks, and more. While ample companies have taken use of this business model and achieved a high growth rate, others have not been able to rightly optimize on the opportunities. Along with several advantages, firms also face certain limitations and challenges related to implementing Ecommerce. It has therefore been concluded that even though various potential benefits are present related to E-commerce, organizations have to develop a critical strategic approach to attain those advantages in an adequate manner. Through effective leadership and the right planning, companies may utilize the opportunities and develop a significant position in the industry.

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